

MAGNETISM AND CATALYSIS. PART V. A MAGNETIC STUDY OF THE CATALYTIC DECOMPOSITION OF POTASSIUM CHLORATE BY COBALTOSIC OXIDE AND FERRO-MAGNETIC VARIETY OF FERRIC OXIDE.

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Catalytic decomposition of potassium chlorate in presence of cobaltosic oxide and ferro-magnetic variety of ferric oxide has been studied from the magnetic point of view. A mechanism of the reaction has been suggested indicating the formation of an intermediate compound with the catalysts.

Number of hypotheses, both chemical as well as mechanical, have been put forth from time to time in order to explain the mechanism of catalytic decomposition of potassium chlorate by oxides. Recently Bhatnagar and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 125) investigated this reaction from the magnetic standpoint and put forth a tentative scheme suggesting the formation of an intermediate complex of manganese. In the present investigation the authors have extended that work to the study of the catalytic decomposition of potassium chlorate in the presence of other oxides, viz., cobaltosic oxide (Co_2O_3) and ferro-magnetic variety of ferric oxide, from the magnetic standpoint.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The susceptibility values were determined on a modified form of Guoy's magnetic balance and the calculation of χ was made according to the equation,

$$\chi_{d_2} = \frac{1}{m_{d_2}} \left[(\chi_{d_1} \cdot m_{d_1} - \chi_s \cdot m_s \cdot d_1) \frac{w_{d_2}}{w_{d_1}} + \chi_s \cdot m_s \cdot d_2 \right]$$

where χ_{d_1} and χ_{d_2} are respectively the specific susceptibilities of the standard substance and of the specimen, w_{d_1} and w_{d_2} are the respective pulls; m_{d_1} and m_{d_2} are the respective masses and $m_s \cdot d_1$ and $m_s \cdot d_2$ are the masses of air displaced respectively by the standard substance and by the specimen.

Materials Used.

Potassium chlorate (extra pure) was recrystallised and its purity ascertained by reducing it to the chloride with sulphur dioxide and estimating the chloride by Volhard's method. Purity was found to be 99.80%. The chlorate gave a susceptibility value of -0.300×10^{-6} (International Critical Tables, $\chi = -0.300 \times 10^{-6}$).

Cobaltous oxide (Co_2O_3) was prepared by heating cobaltous oxalate to redness in air in a Gallen Kemp's electric furnace (Rammelsberg, *Pogg. Ann.*, 1849, 78, 93). The oxide obtained was in the form of a black powder. Its purity was ascertained by the analysis of cobalt by the electrolytic deposition method (Found: Co, 73.38. Calc. 73.43%). The observed value of the magnetic susceptibility was $+30.63 \times 10^{-6}$ at 20°. In literature, however, divergent values of susceptibility varying between 32.00×10^{-6} and 43.6×10^{-6} are reported (cf. Herroun and Wilson, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1921, 33A, 204; Hansknecht, "Magnet Chemische Untersuchungen," Strassburg, 1914, p. 38; Merck and Wedekind, "Handbueh der Krystallographisch-physikalischen Chemie", Leipzig, 1930, 186, 49). The reason for this divergence will be discussed in a subsequent paper.

Ferro-magnetic variety of ferric oxide was prepared from the ordinary red variety of Fe_2O_3 which was prepared by precipitating the ferric hydroxide from ferric chloride by the addition of ammonia and further igniting the ferric hydroxide to the oxide state at 500° in an electric furnace (Found: Fe, 69.9. Calc. 70%). Pure and dry hydrogen was then passed over the red Fe_2O_3 at 500° in an electric furnace, when it transformed into Fe_3O_4 and was further oxidised gently by a slow current of dry air at 200°–250° for 2 hours (Found: Fe, 69.88. Calc. 70.0%).

The susceptibility of an intimate mixture of potassium chlorate and the catalyst approximately in the ratio of 4 : 1, were determined after analysis. It was then heated at different temperatures (below the temperature of spontaneous ignition) for different intervals of time, its χ -value determined and the products analysed at each stage.

Methods of Estimation.

Chloride and Chlorate.—The mixture was treated with water till free of chloride and chlorate and the filtrate made to a known volume. Chloride was estimated by Volhard's method and the chlorate was reduced to chloride in an aliquot portion with sulphur dioxide and the chloride estimated as above.

Cobaltous oxide was estimated by the electrolytic method and the active oxygen determined in the insoluble residue iodometrically.

Ferric oxide was estimated by precipitation as hydroxide followed by ignition to Fe_2O_3 .

Results so obtained are set forth in Tables I and II. The values in each case represent the mean of at least three observations.

Since the composition of the mixture and the susceptibilities of its components at various stages are known, the theoretical values of χ are those arrived at on the additivity law for a mixture.

TABLE I.

Catalytic decomposition of KClO_3 with Co_3O_4 as a catalyst.

Temp. = 20° . χ of $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4 = +30.63 \times 10^{-6}$. χ of $\text{KClO}_3 = -0.306 \times 10^{-6}$.
 χ of $\text{KCl} = -0.516 \times 10^{-6}$.

Composition of the solid residue.							Magnetic susceptibility values ($\chi \times 10^6$).		
MIXTURE I.									
No.	Temp.	Time.	Co_3O_4 .	KClO_3 .	KCl .	Total.	Found. (a)	Calc. (b)	Diff. (a-b).
1.	—	—	18.25%	81.70%	0.00%	99.95%	5.332	5.346	-0.014
2.	290-300°	0.5 hr.	19.13	77.54	3.22	99.89	5.320	5.609	-0.289
3.	300-310°	0.5	20.98	63.21	15.66	99.85	5.857	6.157	-0.300
4.	310-320°	0.5	22.44	52.51	24.86	99.83	6.282	6.588	-0.306
5.	320-330°	0.5	24.12	39.81	35.92	99.85	6.782	7.084	-0.302
6.	330-345°	Spontaneous.	26.30	0.00	73.68	99.98	7.676	7.696	-0.020
MIXTURE II.									
1.	—	—	18.25%	81.72%	0.00%	99.77%	5.334	5.346	-0.012
2.	290-300°	0.5	19.13	77.55	3.20	99.88	5.321	5.609	-0.288
3.	300-310°	0.5	21.00	63.38	15.70	99.89	5.848	6.148	-0.300
4.	310-320°	0.5	22.60	52.27	25.01	99.88	6.332	6.637	-0.305
5.	320-330°	0.5	24.13	39.80	35.92	99.85	6.784	7.084	-0.300
6.	330-345°	Spontaneous.	26.33	0.00	73.67	100.0	7.672	7.687	-0.015

TABLE II.

Catalytic decomposition of $KClO_3$ with ferro-magnetic variety of Fe_2O_3 .

Temp. = 20°.

Magnetic nature of the mixture I and II is ferromagnetic.

Composition of the solid residue.

No.	Temp.	Time. hrs.	Fe_2O_3 .	$KClO_3$.	KCl.	Total.	Fe_2O_3 .	$KClO_3$.	KCl.	Total.
			MIXTURE I.				MIXTURE II.			
1	—	—	16.1%	83.92%	0.00%	100.02%	17.23%	82.77%	0.00%	100.00%
2	255-265°	0.5	16.77	78.09	4.04	99.90	18.55	77.01	4.33	99.89
3	270-280°	0.5	18.54	70.97	10.37	99.88	19.84	69.23	10.86	99.93
4	290-300°	0.5	20.47	58.06	21.32	99.85	21.63	56.21	22.02	99.86
5	310-320°	0.5	21.83	43.11	34.92	99.86	23.03	41.08	35.73	99.84
6	320-330°	Spontaneous.	23.03	0.00	76.96	99.99	25.12	0.00	74.81	99.93

In the case of both the catalysts a separate aliquot portion of the mixture was taken and heated in a closed tube for about half an hour upto the temperature of the spontaneous decomposition of the mixture. The gases evolved in the reaction were bubbled through potassium iodide solution in order to see if any chlorine was liberated from the mixture. It was observed that not a trace of free iodine was liberated and hence no trace of chlorine was set free in the case of the catalytic decomposition of the two mixtures.

DISCUSSION.

The numerous theories which have been advanced from time to time to explain the reaction mechanism of the catalytic decomposition of potassium chlorate by oxides are either (a) mechanical or (b) chemical in nature.

The untenability of the mechanical hypothesis has been discussed (Bhatnagar and co-workers, *loc. cit.*). Psarshevshi (*Sci. Mag. Chem. Cath. Katerinoslav*, 1926, p. 165) while investigating the catalytic decomposition of potassium chlorate by oxides suggested that the adsorbed gases are ionised by the impacts of electrons on the catalysts and thereafter act upon the salt.

To explain the mechanism of the catalytic decomposition of KClO_3 by MnO_2 and Fe_2O_3 , Bhatnagar and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) put forward the view that an intermediate compound was formed. They consequently suggested a tentative scheme which explained the evolution of chlorine, formation of traces of permanganate and the formation of the complex oxides of manganese. The scheme suggested was of the nature of a cycle of changes which ultimately result in the release of MnO_2 .

The magnetic results tabulated in Table I also conclusively show that an intermediate compound is formed in the catalysed decomposition of potassium chlorate by cobaltous oxide and the oxide takes part in the reaction. Furthermore it is clear that the observed paramagnetic susceptibility value of the reaction mixture at the intermediate stages is lower than the value calculated on the mixture law and consequently the alleged intermediate compound must be either diamagnetic or at least less paramagnetic than the original oxide.

The behaviour of catalytic decomposition of potassium chlorate by cobaltous oxide differs from the decomposition when manganese dioxide is used as a catalyst in as much as that in this case no trace of chlorine is evolved. It suggests that the reaction mechanism of catalysed decomposition by cobaltous oxide is different from that suggested for the catalysed decomposition of KClO_3 by MnO_2 .

Sodeau (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 1066) in trying to explain the role of MnO_2 in the catalytic decomposition of KClO_3 suggested that there was an alternate formation and breaking up of different oxides of manganese.

The behaviour of cobaltous oxide can be similarly explained by suggesting the formation and breaking up of such oxide as Co_2O_3 , etc. The following scheme can be suggested which would readily explain the magnetic results (Table I) because pure cobaltous oxide has molecular susceptibility per metallic atom of Co as $2460 \cdot 0 \times 10^{-6}$ and pure cobaltic oxide (Co_2O_3) has molecular susceptibility value per metallic atom of Co as $2375 \cdot 0 \times 10^{-6}$ which is lower than the original Co_3O_4 . Moreover, it is known that cobaltic oxide has great tendency to change to cobaltous oxide. Therefore cobaltic oxide as soon as formed is at once changed to Co_2O_3 .

The following scheme is hence suggested :—

When the ferro-magnetic variety of ferric oxide was used as a catalyst, it was observed (Table II) that the spontaneous decomposition temperature of potassium chlorate was 330° , whereas Bhatnagar, Parkash and Singh (*loc. cit.*) observed that with the ordinary variety of ferric oxide the spontaneous decomposition temperature was 350° .

The lowering in the spontaneous decomposition temperature of KClO_3 by $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ indicates that $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ is a better catalyst than ordinary $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$. This inference is in accord with that of Welo and Bandisch (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1925, 49, 961) who observed that cubic ferro-magnetic $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ behaved as a better catalyst than trigonal variety in the oxidation of benzidine by hydrogen peroxide.

The magnetic measurements of the mixture of KClO_3 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ are not given as this work is in progress.

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